

Analysis of Employee Behavior, Environmentally Friendly Intellectuals, and the Advantages of Green Motivation Towards Green Innovation in the DKI Jakarta Provincial Tourism Office

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ABSTRACT

At this time, tourism is the most interesting thing for local and international tourists to visit. The world of tourism was not running due to the impact of Covid 19 in the previous 2 years, but now tourism has become the main attraction after the Covid 19 period has passed. Of course, each region has different attractions in terms of tourism. DKI Jakarta Province has interesting attractions to visit, there are many small islands that are beautiful to the eye, and attractive as a place to relieve fatigue. Therefore, it needs to be supported by environmentally friendly employee behavior, environmentally friendly intellectuals, and superior green motivation, which aims to increase green innovation in this place. The aim of this research is to examine the influence between environmentally friendly employee behavior and green innovation, examine the influence between green intellectuals and green innovation, and examine the influence between green competitive advantage and green innovation. On this occasion, the researcher wants to see the extent of the influence of the employee behavior variable (X1), friendly intellectuals (X2), and the superiority of green motivation (X3) towards green innovation (Y) in DKI Jakarta Province. This research method is a literature review that compares several existing theories with previous research. The output of this research was submitted to an international journal, namely Copernicus

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is the most interesting thing for local and international tourists to visit (Ansari et al., 2021). Two years earlier, the impact of Covid 19 caused the tourism industry to stop functioning;

However, after the Covid 19 period ended, tourism emerged as a major attraction. (Aluko et al., 2021). Each region has a different attraction in terms of tourism, the environment is not only a place to live but also as a resource for the continuity and continuity of industrial activities themselves (Amoako, 2020).

However, without realizing it, the environment is being damaged by the company's activities (Asiaei et al., 2022). Company waste and activities have a negative impact and cause damage to the environment (Astuti & Wahyuni, 2018). Water, land and air pollution, landfilling of waste that exceeds capacity, global warming, ecosystem damage, the emergence of various diseases, floods and other natural disasters are examples of damage that has been done to the environment. . The worst example is the earth which is on the verge of destruction (Anwar et al., 2020).

The environmental issues above are a very serious problem, the community and government are also paying serious attention and taking action towards this matter (Asadi et al., 2020).

Companies have a big contribution to make regarding the increasingly deteriorating natural environment. A green environment does not always have to be zero pollution, industry must encourage green production in its activities (Benevene & Buonomo, 2020).

Several studies reveal factors that can influence either directly or indirectly corporate green competitive advantage, namely: researching employee eco-friendly behavior in green human resources management which supports green environmental performance and competitive advantage of a company or organization (Chaudhary , 2020).

Meanwhile, research examining the Green Intellectual Capital factor in research on Green Intellectual Capital is linked to green motivation, green innovation and green environmental performance which will later create a tourism situation that has good competitiveness (A'yuni & Muafi, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Author and Year	Definitions
Widiyati & Murwaningsari, 2021	Companies must have innovative products so that profits increase and have an advantage in competition. Currently innovation in companies is a necessity, and many innovations are related to things that are environmentally friendly
A'yuni & Muafi, 2020	Green Intellectual Capital factor in research on Green Intellectual Capital is linked to green motivation, green

innovation and green environmental performance which will later create a tourism situation that has good competitiveness

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework (images must be in good quality)

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of writing this article is to review and summarize the literature review related to the implementation of employee engagement in multinational companies, so that they know what factors can be effectively used to increase employee engagement through various methods, other career factors, transactions. management, Recruitment, Organizational Commitment, researchers attempt to read, analyze and summarize literature reviews from various journals and other related information sources to determine a strategy to implement effective employee engagement in an organization. This study uses a literature review approach to achieve the research objectives. The mini-assessment of employee engagement is conducted by reading and analyzing several peer-reviewed journal articles. This research method is a literature review that compares several existing theories and previous studies. To obtain the information and data necessary for this work, the following data collection methods are used: Documents/Library, ie. a data collection technique for researching documents related to the researched problem. The data analysis method of this study uses the literature review analysis method using an inductive reasoning model. The analysis process is carried out using a data analysis technique, which is content analysis. In other words, a detailed description of data and context, their nature, characteristics, content, reasoning, and the use of inductive logic to draw conclusions

RESULTS

Previous literature shows that green competitive advantage is supported by determining predictors such as; factors of Green Human Resource Management, Green Marketing, Green Intellectual Capital and so on (Gupta & Gupta, 2020). This research uses several independent variables to explain the relationship and influence on the creation of Green Competitive Advantage for manufacturing companies that are the object of research (Hadjri et al., 2020). Employee environmentally friendly behavior is called environmental Organizational Organizational Citizenship behavior (OCBEi) and is a voluntary individual action that leads to effective environmental performance in an organization (Purnama et al., 2021).

Based on the 2022 Green Industry Report, research shows that as many as 55% of consumers in 60 countries pay more for environmentally friendly products (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2021). At least 71% of Americans, according to one definition, think about the environment when they travel. From current green business practices, green functional areas and green human resource management have been balanced (Majiid et al., 2022).

Motivation to win the competition is needed by manufacturing companies to continue to survive in business, management and employees have an important role in fostering motivation to keep the company environment green so that they can enjoy work and success for a long time (Ahmed et al., 2021). Companies must have innovative products so that profits increase and have an advantage in competing. Nowadays, innovation in companies is a necessity, and many innovations are related to things that are environmentally friendly (Wiidiyatii & Murwaniingsarii, 2021). The overall competitiveness of a company is positively influenced by the components of environmental product innovation and environmental process innovation (Hang et al., 2022).

DISCUSSION

Employee behavior is something that is important for an employee in a company to achieve green innovation at the DKI Jakarta Provincial Tourism Office. Environmentally friendly intellectuals are of course also very necessary to be able to increase green innovation. Likewise, the superiority of green motivation will greatly support the achievement of the vision and mission of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Tourism Office.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research suggests that companies can improve all the variables in this research in order to increase their research.

FURTHER STUDY

for future researchers to be able to add variables that match the dependent variable.

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